

Report

Electric lighting for classrooms:
Photometric and energy use calculation for
four lighting fixture and layout alternatives

Prepared by:

Hamidreza Eizadi, Stavroula Angelaki,
Ute Besenecker

Stockholm,
June 2025

Cover illustration: Stavroula Angelaki

This work is part of LiSE, a research project on Lighting in School Environments.

Corresponding author:

Hamidreza Eizadi

eizadi@kth.se

Funding: The following work was funded by Energimyndigheten (50803-1) and Bertil & Britt Svenssons Belysningsstiftelsen (2020-vår29) . Funding acquired by Ute Besenecker.

Acknowledgements: The authors thank Ken Appleman for editing support of the document.

All figures and illustrations were created by the authors unless otherwise stated.

ARCHITECTURAL
LIGHTING
DESIGN

Contents

- 1** Introduction
- 2** Assumptions and considerations used in the simulations and calculations to simplify comparison
- 3** Analysis and discussion
 - Alt 1. Pendants with florescent tubes
 - Alt 2. Pendants with LED Tubes
 - Alt 3. LED Panels 60*60 cm
 - Alt 4. LED Pendants and Spotlights with control system
- 4** Result summary
- 5** Conclusion
- 6** References
- 7** Table of Figures
- 8** Appendix

Introduction

1.

The energy consumption of electric lighting systems plays an important role in the overall energy usage of any building, including in schools and educational spaces. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on energy efficient, sustainable lighting solutions to minimize environmental impact and optimize operational costs as well. Current technological advancements, specifically related to LED technology and control systems enabled the replacement of fluorescent lighting in work spaces and educational environments.

This report compares different lighting systems following ceiling grid-based lighting placements. The report presents an overview based on simulating and comparing the lighting energy consumption in two classrooms at a school located in central Sweden (Figure 1). Specifically, it compares the simulated energy and photometric performance of several different lighting technologies and related layouts, including fluorescent tubes, LED retrofit tubes, off-the-shelf diffuse LED panels (60x60 cm), and a configuration of round LED up-down pendent fixtures. For the purpose of the comparison, daylighting is disregarded in this report.

For comparison, the various alternatives were used throughout two simulated classrooms to estimate and compare the performance and energy characteristics related to electric lighting. The calculations were conducted using Dialux Evo - version 11.1 and compared to lighting standard EN 12464-1:2021 (Figure 4). The lighting simulations are based on the real-world conditions at a school, and it needs to be stated that existing lighting layout prior to LED lighting installations in 2023 were installed while EN 12464-1:2011 was in place. The required light levels on the working surfaces differ from each other in these two documents, with the newer one requiring, for example, 500 lux since 2021 instead of the 300 lux prior (since 2011).

The modelling of the classroom spaces, layouts, materials, and other elements was based on the actual existing conditions at a school. The classrooms' layouts typically vary throughout the year, however for the purpose of this report one layout was used for all lighting calculations. The final part of this report presents a comparison between the different scenarios.

Assumptions ...

2.

... and considerations used in the simulations and calculations to enable comparison.

Lighting Fixture Types: In this report, each alternative is based on a different luminaire. The first one (linear florescent pendant) considered a now outdated solution (Alt.1) which used to be the main light source in the classrooms and is still operating in some of them at the time of writing this report. In the second alternative, linear LED retrofits were used in the same luminaire layouts, and the third alternative is using off-the-shelf diffuse LED panels (60x60) (Alt.3) that were procured and installed in one of the classrooms as alternative to the linear retrofits. In addition to these configurations, a lighting system using a combination of up-down pendants and spotlighting was added (Alt. 4) enabling several different scenarios with distinct photometric profiles and varying energy use. All fixture specification cut sheets can be found in the Appendix.

Lighting Load: The power rating or wattage of lighting fixture in Alt.1 and Alt.3 are based on existing products used in the school. For Alt.2 a LED tube from the same manufacturer (with the most compatibility with the existing fixture), was used in the calculations. For Alt. 4 new luminaires were proposed.

Operating Hours: The comparison of energy consumption in this report is based on the hourly rate demand of the luminaires, and estimated hours of operation of the school throughout one year (see Figure 26). However, it has to be considered that regular operational hours, as well as any additional hours when lighting might be required for extracurricular activities or evening events, and other parameters, such as daylight and user behavior, will affect the actual overall monthly and annual consumption.

Lighting Control Systems: Implementing lighting control systems with occupancy sensors, timers, or daylight harvesting sensors, can affect energy consumption. Since in the existing conditions of the school there were no control option other than manual switching, alternatives 1-3 were calculated using the same condition. Alternative 4 which was based on a lighting system with several scenarios, however, included variations.

Lighting Zoning and Area Classification: Considering the same function in the sample classrooms of this report, a similar utilization profile is assigned to all the rooms (44. Educational buildings, 1. Classroom- general activities) Fig.5.

Lighting Fixture Information: Some assumptions were made about the existing products employed in the school, and the closest available lighting data files were selected and modified if needed using the LDT Editor Tool based on the technical information obtained.

Annual hours and energy consumption: There are a set of limitations related to the calculation and use of the Dialux Evo software. Due to the nature and use pattern of school environments, specific parameters are not included in the software simulations. Figure 1 illustrates two colour-coded calendars for 2023 and 2024 based on information received from the school for grades 4-6. The working days are coloured light green. School and public holidays are coloured in darker green, and the first and last school days are coloured in orange. The total number of days per year is one hundred and seventy-nine. School days start at 08:00 and end at 14:00, resulting in six hours per day minus one hour for the lunch break. According to the current schedules of the school participating in the research project, some days end at 13:00 and others at 14:50. As a result, an average of 14:00 o'clock is used as an ending time.

As shown in Figure 1, the total number of hours per week is twenty-five. From these hours, four are subtracted related to courses taking place in spaces other than the regular classroom investigated in this report. That leaves a total of twenty-one hours per week. An annual estimation is approximately 3759 hours which is used subsequently to estimate the yearly light and energy use.

Limitations: The above assumptions can be seen as limitations, as this comparison uses assumptions and estimations for certain grades and actual real-world use would need to be site monitored/tracked throughout the year.

2023

JULY

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
26	27	28	29	30	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31	1	2	3	4	5	6

AUGUST

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
31	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29	30	31	1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10

SEPTEMBER

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
28	29	30	31	1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	1
2	3	4	5	6	7	8

OCTOBER

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
25	26	27	28	29	30	1
2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9	10	11	12	13	14	15
16	17	18	19	20	21	22
23	24	25	26	27	28	29
30	31	1	2	3	4	5

NOVEMBER

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
30	31	1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10

DECEMBER

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
27	28	29	30	1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Academic calendar

JANUARY

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	31	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11

FEBRUARY

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
29	30	31	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10

MARCH

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
26	27	28	29	1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

APRIL

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12

MAY

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
29	30	1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	31	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9

JUNE

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
27	28	29	30	31	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

JULY

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	31	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11

AUGUST

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
29	30	31	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30	31	1
2	3	4	5	6	7	8

No of working days

Month	No of working days
Jan	18
Feb	21
Mar	15
Apr	18
May	20
Jun	6
Aug	6
Sep	21
Oct	20
Nov	19
Dec	15
2023	81

No of working days

Month	No of working days
Jan	18
Feb	21
Mar	15
Apr	18
May	20
Jun	6
Aug	6
Sep	21
Oct	20
Nov	19
Dec	15
2024	98

Daily schedule

8:00-14:00=6h - 1h(lunch)=5h (per day) x 5 = 25h
 2h Gym per week
 1h Music per week
 1h Arts per week

25-4=21h per week

Annual (days)	Annual (hours)
179	3759

Colour code

- Work days
- Holidays
- Start/End day

Figure 1: Academic calendar showing an approximation of the total number of hours that lighting is needed.

Figure 2: Plan view, Second Floor, selected classrooms used for the simulation are indicated in colour.

Figure 3 illustrates the various lighting layout corresponding to a fluorescent configuration and several alternate LED scenarios that were installed in the actual school between 2021-2024. These configuration also provided the base for the calculations and comparisons described in this report.

The reflected ceiling plan on the left side of Figure 3 corresponds to conditions found in the school in 2021/22. The layout is based on a grid configuration and there are four different types of lighting fixtures. The ceiling plan on the right corresponds to a new install in 2023/24, during which pendant lighting was replaced in two out of four classrooms.

For the purpose of this report, each simulation to compare the performance of the lighting scenario assumed one typology throughout all spaces, which was not the case in the real-world site installation.

Figure 3: Reflected ceiling plan of actual school conditions with varying systems per room. (A reflected ceiling plan illustrates the Baseline lighting configuration and the alternate light layout.)

Active utilisation profile	
Type of use	
Space	44 Educational premises - Educational buildings
Application	44.1 Classroom - general activities
Illuminance	
Maintenance values	
Visual task (E_m)	500.0 lx Modify
Visual task modified ($E_{m,mod}$)	1000.0 lx
Surrounding area (E_m)	300.0 lx
Background area (E_m)	100.0 lx
Cylindrical ($E_{m,z}$)	150.0 lx
Wall ($E_{m,wall}$)	150.0 lx
Ceiling ($E_{m,ceiling}$)	100.0 lx
Uniformity (E_{min}/E_m)	0.600
Glare limitation	
Indoors (R_{UGL})	19
Use times	
Day	1398 Hours per year ~3.83 Hours per day
Night	2 Hours per year ~0.01 Hours per day
Absence factor	0.25
Partial operation factor of the building operation time for lighting	0.90
Begin Time	8 o'clock
End Time	15 o'clock
Days per Week	5
Maintenance and miscellaneous	
Colour rendering index (R_a)	80
Height of working plane	0.80 m
Reduction factor (task area)	0.97
Height for measuring the cylindrical illuminance	1.20 m
Inspection interval	1.0 Years
Ambient condition	Clean
Maintenance interval for luminaires	3.0 Years
Replacement interval for lamps	1.0 Years
Individual replacement of failed lamps	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Table 44 — Educational premises - Educational buildings

Ref. no.	Type of task/activity area	\bar{E}_m lx		U_o	R_a	R_{UGL}	$\bar{E}_{m,z}$ lx	$\bar{E}_{m,wall}$ lx	$\bar{E}_{m,ceiling}$ lx	Specific requirements
		required ^a	modified ^b							
44.1	Classroom - General activities	500	1 000	0,60	80	19	150	150	100	Lighting should be controllable, see 6.2.4, for different activities and scene settings. For classrooms used by young children, an \bar{E}_m required of 300 lx may be used by dimming (see 5.3.3). Ambient light should be considered, see Annex B, room brightness, see 6.7.
44.2	Auditorium, lecture halls	500	750	0,60	80	19	150	150	50	Lighting should be controllable, see 6.2.4, to accommodate various A/V needs, room brightness, see 6.7.
44.3	Attending lecture in seating areas in auditoriums and lecture halls	200	300	0,60	80	19	75	75	50	Reduction by dimming, DSE-work, see 5.9.
44.4	Black green and white boards	500	750	0,70	80	19	-	-	-	Vertical illuminances. Specular reflections shall be prevented. Presenter/teacher shall be illuminated with suitable vertical illuminance.

Figure 4: Relevant information from the EN 12464-1:2021 Lighting Standards – Educational spaces

Figure 5: Utilization profile used for the classrooms Dialux calculation.

Analysis

3.

After running photometric and energy use calculations for the two classrooms using four different alternatives throughout all spaces, the following results were extracted from the Dialux reports:

Alt. 1 Pendant with florescent tubes, Light source specification

Article No.	NI-T836W 840 G13
P	72.0 W
Φ_{Lamp}	6700 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	4467 lm
η	66.67 %
Luminous efficacy	62.0 lm/W
CCT	4000 K
CRI	80

Figure 6: Specification of Florescent tubes used in the classrooms.

Figure 7: Room 31 with pendants using fluorescent tubes.

Alt. 1 Pendant with florescent tubes/Calculation for each room

Room 31

P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{perpendicular}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No.	P
864.0 W	66.18 m ²	13.05 W/m ² = 1.61 W/m ² /100 lx (Room)	813 lx	12	NI-T836W	72.0 W

Room 32

P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{perpendicular}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No.	P
648.0 W	61.19 m ²	10.59 W/m ² = 1.62 W/m ² /100 lx (Room)	652 lx	9	NI-T836W	72.0 W

Table 1: Calculation of energy and illumination in each room with the use of pendants using fluorescent tubes.

Pendant with florescent tubes /Room 31-32 /Illumination

Figure 8: Isolux plan of room 31 with the use of pendants using fluorescent tubes.

Figure 9: Isolux plan of room 32 with the use of pendants using fluorescent tubes.

Alt. 2 Pendant with LED tubes

Article No.	43719852
P	48.5 W
Φ_{Lamp}	8400 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	3181 lm
η	37.87 %
Luminous efficacy	65.6 lm/W
CCT	4000 K
CRI	80

Figure 10: Specification of LED tubes used in the classrooms.

Figure 11: Room 32 classroom with pendants using retrofit LED tube lighting.

Alt. 2 Pendant with LED tubes/Calculation for each room

Room 31

P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{perpendicular}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No.	P
582.0 W	66,18 m ²	8.79 W/m ² = 1.52 W/m ² /100 lx (Room)	580 lx	12	LED T8 NEO 58 840/G13	48.5 W

Room 32

P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{perpendicular}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No.	P
436.5 W	61,19 m ²	7.13 W/m ² = 1.53 W/m ² /100 lx (Room)	465 lx	9	LED T8 NEO 58 840/G13	48.5 W

Table 2: Calculation of energy and illumination in each room with the use of pendants using retrofit LED tubes.

Pendant with LED tubes /Room 31-32 /Illumination

Figure 12: Isolux plan of room 31 with the use of pendants using retrofit LED tubes.

Figure 13: Isolux plan of room 32 with the use of pendants using retrofit LED tubes.

Alt. 3 LED Panels 60x60cm

Article No.	GWF1611MN840
P	33.0 W
$\Phi_{\text{Luminaire}}$	3315 lm
Luminous efficacy	100.5 lm/W
CCT	3936 K
CRI	80

Figure 14: Specification of LED panels used in the classrooms.

Figure 15: Room 31 classroom with LED panel lighting.

Alt. 3 LED Panels 60x60cm/Calculation for each room

Room 31

P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{\text{perpendicular}}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No.	P
264.0 W	66,18 m ²	3.99 W/m ² = 1.01 W/m ² /100 lx (Room)	396 lx	12	GWF1611	72.0 W

Room 32

P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{\text{perpendicular}}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No.	P
297.0 W	61,19 m ²	4.85 W/m ² = 0.81 W/m ² /100 lx (Room)	599 lx	9	GWF1611	72.0 W

Table 3: Calculation of energy and illumination in each room with the use of LED panels.

LED Panels 60x60cm /Room 31-32 /Illumination

Figure 16: Isolux plan of room 31 with the use of retro. LED panels.

Figure 17: Isolux plan of room 32 with the use of retro. LED panels.

Alt. 4 Customized LED Pendants

Article No.	004-MOD-580
P	60.0 W
Φ_{Lamp}	9201 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	7723 lm
η	83.93 %
Luminous efficacy	128.7 lm/W
CCT	4000 K
CRI	90

Figure 18: Specification of LED pendants used in the classrooms.

Figure 19: Room 32 with LED pendant lighting.

Alt. 4 LED Pendants and Spotlights /Calculation for each room and scene

Room 31

Light scene	P_{total}	A_{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{perpendicular}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No. (for all scenes)
1	620.2 W	66.18 m ²	9.38 W/m ² = 1.41 W/m ² /100 lx	664 lx	12	ATLAS-DIR30 MEDIUM ¹
2	538.2 W		8.14 W/m ² = 1.32 W/m ² /100 lx	618 lx	10	+
3	403.2 W		6.09 W/m ² = 1.29 W/m ² /100 lx	472 lx	12	ATLAS-IND 930 ²
4	464.2 W		7.02 W/m ² = 1.36 W/m ² /100 lx	516 lx	10	+
5	45.0 W		0.67 W/m ² = 0.79 W/m ² /100 lx	85 lx	4	26122-XFZ3 ³
6	312.5 W		4.72 W/m ² = 1.27 W/m ² /100 lx	372 lx	12	

Table 4a : Calculation of energy and illumination in each room with the use LED Pendants and spotlights.

¹P = 17.5 W

²P = 55.1 W

³P = 30.0 W

Room 32

Light scene	P _{total}	A _{Room}	Lighting power density	$\bar{E}_{\text{perpendicular}}$ (Working plane)	Luminaire pcs.	Article No. (for all scenes)
1	620.2 W	61,19 m ²	10.14 W/m ² = 1.34 W/m ² /100 lx	757 lx	12	ATLAS-DIR30 MEDIUM + ATLAS-IND 930 + 26122-XFZ3
2	538.2 W		8.18 W/m ² = 1.17 W/m ² /100 lx	697 lx	10	
3	403.2 W		6.16 W/m ² = 1.12 W/m ² /100 lx	549 lx	12	
4	464.2 W		7.16 W/m ² = 1.21 W/m ² /100 lx	594 lx	10	
5	45 W		0.74 W/m ² = 0.71 W/m ² /100 lx	104 lx	4	
6	312.5 W		5.11 W/m ² = 1.17 W/m ² /100 lx	435 lx	12	

Table 4b : Calculation of energy and illumination in each room with the use LED Pendants and spotlights.

Alt. 4 Scenarios /Additional characteristics

Space	Light scene	Number of luminaires	Energy estimation (kWh/a) ¹	Power total (w)	Avg. E p (lux) ²	Area (m ²)	Light power density (w/m ²)
31	1	12	2335	620.2 W	664	66.18	9.37 W/m ²
	2	10	2026	538.2 W	618		8.13 W/m ²
	3	12	1517	403.2 W	472		6.09 W/m ²
	4	10	1747	464.2 W	516		7.01 W/m ²
	5	4	169	45 W	85		0.68 W/m ²
	6	12	1175	312.5 W	372		4.72 W/m ²

Space	Light scene	Number of luminaires	Energy estimation (kWh/a) ¹	Power total (w)	Avg. E p (lux) ²	Area (m ²)	Light power density (w/m ²)
32	1	12	2335	620.2 W	757	61.19	10.14 W/m ²
	2	10	2026	538.2 W	697		8.80 W/m ²
	3	12	1517	403.2 W	549		6.59 W/m ²
	4	10	1747	464.2 W	594		7.59 W/m ²
	5	4	169	45 W	104		0.74 W/m ²
	6	12	1175	312.5 W	435		5.11 W/m ²

Table 5: Results from Dialux EVO based on the on-site installation.

¹ Calculated using DIN:18599-4. Target value is max. 2150 kWh/a per room. Hours of operations estimated based on annual usage pattern illustrated in Figure 26.

² Target value \geq 500 lx as per EN 12464-1:2021

LED Pendants and Spotlights /Room 31-32 /Illumination

1. Group work

2. Individual work

3. Presentation

4. Laptop

Figure 20: Isolux plan for rooms 31 and 32 corresponding to 4 light scenes. The light scenes 5. (Movie) and 6. (Movie and Discussion) only involve the spotlighting in addition to screens and are not illustrated here. (Source: Authors)

1. Group work

2. Individual work

3. Presentation

4. Laptop

5. Movie

6. Movie & Discussion

Figure 21: Dialux renderings and on-site photographs for the six light scenes installed at the school (Room 31)

Figure 22: Dialux renderings and on-site photographs for the six light scenes installed at the school (Room 32).

Alt. 4 Lighting Controls

For this report the software Dialux 11.1 evo is used to simulate and estimate energy use over one year for the four alternate scenarios. However, the lighting scenes in Alt. 4, corresponding to the installation of new LED lights, include control options with different light output per scene.

Lighting scenes were designed to better support different educational activities, following the teachers' input and the researchers' observation studies. Therefore, it is necessary to take into consideration how to compare a uniform scenario with no variation in light level (Alt. 1-3), and a scenario where lighting does not need to be used at full output in order to result in a meaningful evaluation that is consistent with the actual energy consumption.

In Alt. 4, different scenes are programmed to vary light levels and relative distribution throughout the space. Therefore, we simulate possible options for a better comparison. These scenes were based on the activity and equipment the pupils and teachers use, therefore the light levels on horizontal and vertical surfaces were adjusted accordingly (Angelaki, S., & Bodin Danielsson, C., 2025).

Explanation of the lighting scenes

There are six lighting scenes in total. Please see below which button corresponds to each scene.

Control panel / Scenes	Scene names	Scene description
	1. Pupils work together in groups.	
	2. Individual work 	2. Pupils work individually writing on paper, drawing or reading.
	3. Presentation 	3. The teacher is presenting or explaining part of the course.
	4. Laptop 	4. Pupils work on their laptops.
	5. Movie 	5. Movie or cinema mode.
	6. Movie & Discussion 	6. Watching a video and having a discussion as part of the course. It can be used when the video needs to be paused and followed by discussion.

Figure 23: Lighting controlled scenarios for Alt. 4 LED Pendants and Spotlights

The ability of using scenes using control systems brings about a complexity when performing lighting calculation.

Following the recommendations from the EN 12464-1:2021 Lighting Standards, the part referring to educational spaces indicates that control systems should be implemented to customize the lighting. Therefore, designing lighting scenes, installing sensors, dimmers and other control components is highly relevant both to the EN 12464-1:2021 and the feedback/requests received by the school administration and the teachers.

Lighting calculations and simulations are a design tool and precede the installation, therefore, typically, field adjustments are needed during/after installation, aiming and commissioning the fixtures on site. Naturally, there might be certain adjustments related to installing and controlling the lights that should be accommodated on-site. As an example, in Figure 23 the six scenarios are illustrated. The scenarios on the upper row depict the proposed relative light/dimming percentages (Figure 23). The scenario on the bottom row shows the adjusted percentages after visual adjustments for perceived brightness that took place during the installation (Figure 23).

	1. Group work	2. Individual work	3. Presentation	4. Laptop	5. Movie	6. Movie & Discussion
Design phase	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)
	50	80	0	0	0	0
	90	60	80	80	0	60
	60	0	80	0	50	90
Installation	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)	Brightness (%)
	60	80	0	0	0	0
	100	90	80	100	0	60
	60 (wall) 100 (window)	0 (wall) 100 (window)	80 (wall) 90 (window)	0 (wall) 80 (window)	70 (wall) 80 (window)	90 (wall) 70 (window)

Figure 24: Comparison of lighting proposal to lighting installation relative light/dimming percentage levels.

Result summary

4.

Metrics/characteristics comparison

Space	Configuration	Number of luminaires	Energy estimation (kWh/a) ¹	Power total (w)	Avg. E p (lux) ²	Area (m ²)	Light power density (w/m ²)
31	Alt 1	12	3247	864	813	66.18	13.06 W/m ²
	Alt 2	12	2188	582	580		8.79 W/m ²
	Alt 3	8	992	264	396		3.99 W/m ²
	Alt4 (Option 1) ³	4-12	1727	45-620	85-664		0.68-9.37 W/m ²
32	Alt 1	9	2435	648	652	61.19	10.59 W/m ²
	Alt 2	9	1640	437	465		7.14 W/m ²
	Alt 3	9	1115	297	599		4.85 W/m ²
	Alt4 (Option 1) ³	4-12	1727	45-620	104-757		0.74-10.13 W/m ²
Both rooms	Alt 1	21	5682	1512	733	127.37	11.87 W/m²
	Alt 2	21	3828	1019	523		8.00 W/m²
	Alt 3	17	2107	561	498		4.40 W/m²
	Alt4 (Option 1) ³	8-24	3454	90-1240	95-711		0.71-9.74 W/m²

Table 6: Overall results of energy calculation and illumination in each room with different light sources.

¹ Calculated using DIN:18599-4. Target value is max. 2150 kWh/a per room. Hours of operations estimated based on annual usage pattern illustrated in Figure 26.

² Target value ≥ 500 lx as per EN 12464-1:2021

³ Alt4 Option 1 estimates one of many possibilities based on the following usage pattern example per year: 20% light scene 1, 20% light scene 2, 25% light scene 3, 20% light scene 4, 5% light scene 5, 10% light scene 6 (see Table 6)

Conclusion

5.

Comparison of estimated power consumption: To compare the four options, we used Alt. 1 as the baseline and calculated the percentage differences for Alt..2, Alt. 3 and Alt.4 (Option 1). It has to be noted that as Alt. 4 has 6 different scenario possibilities that the teachers can use based on learning activity, variations in use and energy consumption are possible. When talking to the teachers, for example, most mentioned that they use only 3 or 4 scenarios out of the 6, however, which options were used varied depending on their preferences, class topic and teaching style. For the comparison in this report, the following assumptions were made:

- For Alt. 1-3, lighting is on during teaching hours
- For Alt. 4, different scenes are used based on learning activities, 20% of the time light scene 1 (Group Work), 20% light scene 2 (Individual Work), 25% light scene 3 (Presentation), 20% light scene 4 (Laptop Work), 5% light scene 5 (Movie), 10% light scene 6 (Movie and Discussion).

Compared to Alt. 1, in terms of power consumption per year (in kWh/a) (see Table 6):

- Alt. 2 has a power consumption that is 33% lower.
- Alt. 3 has a power consumption that is 63% lower.
- Alt. 4 has a power consumption that is 39% lower.

This indicates that all LED based solutions come with energy savings, and that the new, scenario based option outperforms a simple retrofit using pendant lighting. While, in terms of energy usage, the light panel installation comes with highest energy reduction, their implementation should be critically evaluated as energy use is not the main factor for choosing a lighting solution. The lighting quality emitted and generated by using this solution has been topic of recent criticism and discussion.

The use of a system enabling varying lighting scenes and light layering will benefit the visual comfort and orientation of the pupils and teachers and help signal what learning activity is on schedule. While all options can fulfill the average of 500 lux on the work plane, Alt. 4 provides indirect light with a direct task light option which makes a significant difference in terms of reducing glare and enhancing visual comfort. In addition, Alt. 4. LED pendants are mounted on a track system which also provides the flexibility of easy modifications of the lighting layouts based on furnishings and activities in each classroom.

References

6.

EN 12464-1:2021, Light and lighting - Lighting of work places - Part 1: Indoor work places

SWEDISH STANDARD · SS-EN 12464-1:2021, Light and lighting - Lighting of work places - Part 1: Indoor work places

S Angelaki, U Besenecker and C B Danielsson, 2023, A review of lighting research in educational spaces, LIGHT-SYMP-2022, IOP Conf. Series.

S Angelaki, C B Danielsson, 2025, Activity-based lighting for schools: A design handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918184>

List of Figures

7.

Figure 1: Academic calendar showing an approximation of the total number of hours that lighting is needed.	7
Figure 2: Plan view, Second Floor, selected classrooms in color. Source: Authors.	8
Figure 3: Reflected ceiling plan.	9
Figure 4: EN 12464-1:2021 Lighting Standards – Educational spaces	9
Figure 5: Utilization profile used for the classrooms Dialux calculation. Source: Authors.	9
Figure 6: Specification of Florescent tubes used in the classrooms. Source: Authors.	10
Figure 7: Room 31 with pendants using fluorescent tubes.	10
Figure 8: Isolux plan of room 31 with the use of Florescent tubes. Source: Authors.	11
Figure 9: Isolux plan of room 32 with the use of Florescent tubes. Source: Authors.	11
Figure 10: Specification of LED tubes used in the classrooms. Source: Authors.	12
Figure 11: Room 32 classroom with pendants using retrofit LED tube lighting	12
Figure 12: Isolux plan of room 31 with the use of retro. LED tubes. Source: Authors.	13
Figure 13: Isolux plan of room 32 with the use of retro. LED tubes. Source: Authors.	13
Figure 14: Specification of LED panels used in the classrooms. Source: Authors.	14
Figure 15: Room 31 classroom with LED panel lighting.	14
Figure 16: Isolux plan of room 31 with the use of retro. LED panels. Source: Authors.	15
Figure 17: Isolux plan of room 32 with the use of retro. LED panels. Source: Authors.	15
Figure 18: Specification of customized LED pendants used in the classrooms. Source: Authors.	16
Figure 19: Room 32 with LED pendant lighting.	16
Figure 20: Isolux plan for room 31 and 32 with the use of customized LED pendants. Source: Authors.	18
Figure 21: Dialux renderings and on-site photographs for the six light scenes installed at the school (Room 32)	19
Figure 22: Dialux renderings and on-site photographs for the six light scenes installed at the school (Room 31).	20
Figure 23: Lighting controlled scenarios for the intervention phase of the school testsbed research project.	21
Figure 24: Comparison of lighting proposal to lighting installation relative light/dimming percentage levels..	22

Appendix

Iggesund Building C - Alt 1. Fluorescent Tubes

8. DIALux

Product data sheet

Radium Fluorescent Tube

Article No.	NI-T836W 840 G13
P	72.0 W
Φ_{Lamp}	6700 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	4467 lm
η	66.67 %
Luminous efficacy	62.0 lm/W
CCT	4000 K
CRI	80

Polar LDC

Glare evaluation according to RUG												
		70	70	50	50	30	70	70	50	50	30	
p Ceiling		50	30	50	30	30	50	30	50	30	30	
p Walls		20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	
p Floor		20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	
Room size X Y		Viewing direction at right angles to lamp axis					Viewing direction parallel to lamp axis					
2H	2H	12.7	13.8	13.0	14.0	14.2	14.7	15.7	14.9	16.0	16.2	
	3H	12.6	13.5	12.9	13.8	14.0	15.0	16.0	15.3	16.2	16.5	
	4H	12.5	13.4	12.8	13.7	13.9	15.1	16.0	15.4	16.2	16.5	
	6H	12.4	13.2	12.8	13.5	13.8	15.1	15.9	15.4	16.2	16.5	
	8H	12.4	13.2	12.7	13.5	13.8	15.1	15.9	15.4	16.2	16.5	
	12H	12.3	13.1	12.7	13.4	13.7	15.0	15.8	15.4	16.1	16.5	
4H	2H	12.8	13.7	13.1	14.0	14.2	14.5	15.4	14.9	15.7	16.0	
	3H	12.7	13.4	13.0	13.7	14.0	15.0	15.7	15.3	16.0	16.4	
	4H	12.6	13.2	13.0	13.6	13.9	15.1	15.8	15.5	16.2	16.5	
	6H	12.5	13.1	12.9	13.5	13.8	15.2	15.8	15.6	16.2	16.6	
	8H	12.5	13.0	12.9	13.4	13.8	15.2	15.8	15.7	16.2	16.6	
	12H	12.4	12.9	12.9	13.3	13.7	15.2	15.7	15.7	16.1	16.5	
8H	4H	12.5	13.1	12.9	13.4	13.9	15.0	15.6	15.5	16.0	16.4	
	6H	12.4	12.9	12.9	13.3	13.8	15.1	15.6	15.6	16.0	16.5	
	8H	12.4	12.8	12.9	13.2	13.7	15.2	15.6	15.6	16.0	16.5	
	12H	12.4	12.7	12.8	13.2	13.7	15.2	15.5	15.7	16.0	16.5	
	12H	4H	12.5	13.0	12.9	13.4	13.8	15.0	15.5	15.4	15.9	16.3
		6H	12.4	12.8	12.9	13.2	13.7	15.1	15.5	15.6	15.9	16.4
8H		12.4	12.7	12.9	13.2	13.7	15.1	15.5	15.6	15.9	16.4	
Variation of the observer position for the luminaire distances S												
S = 1.0H		+2.4 / -8.6					+1.4 / -1.6					
S = 1.5H		+4.2 / -13.4					+1.8 / -3.6					
S = 2.0H		+6.0 / -16.0					+3.2 / -4.5					
Standard table		BK00					BK01					
Correction summand		-7.1					-4.3					
Corrected glare indices referring to 6700lm Total luminous flux												

RUG diagram (SHR: 0.25)

F

3350

4000K

20 000h

Dimmable

General Data

Article No.	31109316
Code	NL-T8 36W/840/G13
Product EAN	4008597093166
Box quantity (pcs.)	25
EAN Box	4008597493164
Gross weight of box in kg	4.66
Length of box in m	1.24
Width of box in m	0.153
Height of box in m	0.147
Product weight	149 g
Product status	● Inactive

Electric Parameters

Rated wattage	36.0 W
Lamp nominal wattage	36 W
Lamp voltage	103 V
Mains voltage	230 V
Nominal current (mA)	430 mA

Electric Parameters

Compensation capacitor for 50Hz operation	4.5 µF
dimnable	Yes

Light Application Parameters

Luminous flux	3350 lm
Rated lamp luminous flux	3350 lm
max. luminous flux at	25 °C
Beam angle	360 °
Luminous efficiency	93.06 lm/W
Radium light colour	white
Code of light color	840
Colour temperature	4000 K
Color rendering index	? 80
Mean luminance	1.2
Lumen maintenance at 2000h	0.96
Lumen maintenance at 4000h	0.94
Lumen maintenance at 6000h	0.93
Lumen maintenance at 8000h	0.91
Lumen maintenance at 12000h	0.91
Lumen maintenance at 16000h	0.90
Lumen maintenance at 20000h	0.89

Service Life

Average nominal lifespan	20000 h
Mean service life, HF 3h cycle	20000 h
Lamp survival factor at 2000h	0.99
Lamp survival factor at 4000h	0.99
Lamp survival factor at 6000h	0.99
Lamp survival factor at 8000h	0.99
Lamp survival factor at 12000h	0.99
Lamp survival factor at 16000h	0.90
Lamp survival factor at 20000h	0.50

Specification

Energylabel notice	old label, no EPREL registration, no EU data sheet
Energy Label A to G	F

Product data sheet

RADIUM- LED T8 NEO 58 840/G13

Article No.	43719852
P	48.5 W
Φ_{Lamp}	8400 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	3181 lm
η	37.87 %
Luminous efficacy	65.6 lm/W
CCT	4000 K
CRI	80

Polar LDC

Glare evaluation according to RUG													
ρ Ceiling	70	70	50	50	30	70	70	50	50	30			
ρ Walls	50	30	50	30	30	50	30	50	30	30			
ρ Floor	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20			
Room size X Y	Viewing direction at right angles to lamp axis					Viewing direction parallel to lamp axis							
2H	2H	11.6	12.7	11.9	12.9	13.1	13.6	14.7	13.9	14.9	15.1		
	3H	11.5	12.4	11.8	12.7	12.9	13.9	14.9	14.2	15.1	15.4		
	4H	11.4	12.3	11.7	12.6	12.8	14.0	14.9	14.3	15.2	15.4		
	6H	11.3	12.2	11.7	12.4	12.7	14.0	14.8	14.4	15.1	15.4		
	8H	11.3	12.1	11.6	12.4	12.7	14.0	14.8	14.3	15.1	15.4		
12H	11.2	12.0	11.6	12.3	12.6	14.0	14.7	14.3	15.0	15.4			
4H	2H	11.7	12.6	12.0	12.9	13.1	13.5	14.4	13.8	14.6	14.9		
	3H	11.6	12.3	11.9	12.6	13.0	13.9	14.6	14.3	15.0	15.3		
	4H	11.5	12.2	11.9	12.5	12.9	14.1	14.7	14.4	15.1	15.4		
	6H	11.4	12.0	11.8	12.4	12.8	14.1	14.7	14.6	15.1	15.5		
	8H	11.4	11.9	11.8	12.3	12.7	14.1	14.7	14.6	15.1	15.5		
12H	11.3	11.8	11.8	12.2	12.7	14.1	14.6	14.6	15.0	15.5			
8H	4H	11.4	12.0	11.8	12.4	12.8	13.9	14.5	14.4	14.9	15.3		
	6H	11.3	11.8	11.8	12.2	12.7	14.1	14.5	14.5	14.9	15.4		
	8H	11.3	11.7	11.8	12.1	12.6	14.1	14.5	14.6	14.9	15.4		
	12H	11.3	11.6	11.8	12.1	12.6	14.1	14.4	14.6	14.9	15.4		
12H	4H	11.4	11.9	11.8	12.3	12.7	13.9	14.4	14.3	14.8	15.2		
	6H	11.3	11.7	11.8	12.2	12.6	14.0	14.4	14.5	14.9	15.3		
	8H	11.3	11.6	11.8	12.1	12.6	14.0	14.4	14.5	14.8	15.3		
Variation of the observer position for the luminaire distances S													
S = 1.0H	+2.4 / -8.6					+1.4 / -1.6							
S = 1.5H	+4.2 / -13.4					+1.8 / -3.6							
S = 2.0H	+6.0 / -16.0					+3.2 / -4.5							
Standard table	BK00					BK01							
Correction summand	-10.1					-7.4							
Corrected glare indices referring to 8400lm Total luminous flux													

RUG diagram (SHR: 0.25)

LED T8 Neo 58 - 840				
Operating current	Voltage	Power	Luminous efficacy	Luminous flux
1 500 mA	20.5 V	30.8 W	168 lm/W	5 180 lm
1 450 mA	20.5 V	29.7 W	169 lm/W	5 017 lm
1 400 mA	20.4 V	28.6 W	170 lm/W	4 853 lm
1 350 mA	20.4 V	27.5 W	170 lm/W	4 690 lm
1 300 mA	20.3 V	26.5 W	171 lm/W	4 527 lm
1 250 mA	20.3 V	25.4 W	172 lm/W	4 363 lm
1 200 mA	20.3 V	24.3 W	173 lm/W	4 200 lm
1 150 mA	20.2 V	23.2 W	174 lm/W	4 038 lm
1 100 mA	20.1 V	22.1 W	175 lm/W	3 875 lm
1 050 mA	20.0 V	21.0 W	176 lm/W	3 713 lm
1 000 mA	20.0 V	20.0 W	178 lm/W	3 550 lm

C

24.3

4000K

70 000h

Dimmable

General Data

Article No.	43719852
Code	RL-T8 58 NEO 840/G13 DC
Product EAN	4008597198526
Box quantity (pcs.)	25
EAN Box	4008597498527
Gross weight of box in kg	7.75
Length of box in m	1.57
Width of box in m	0.21
Height of box in m	0.2
Product weight	200 g
Product status	● Active

Electric Parameters

Rated wattage	24.3 W
Nominal power	24.3 W
Weighted energy consumption in 1,000 hours	25 kWh
Lamp power	20.0-30.8 W
Nominal voltage	19.5-21.5 V

Electric Parameters

Voltage type	DC
Nominal current	1000-1500 mA
Nominal current (mA)	1200 mA

Light Application Parameters

Rated luminous flux acc. IEC 62722-2-1	4200 lm
Luminous flux	3550-5180 lm
max. luminous flux	5180 lm
max. luminous flux at	1500 mA
Beam angle	160 °
Luminous efficiency	173 lm/W
Radium light colour	coolwhite
Color temperature	4000 K
Color coordinate X	0.380
Color coordinate Y	0.380
Color rendering index	> 80
Color Stability	≤ 5 sdc _m

Service Life

Average nominal lifespan	70000 h
T _c Temperature max.	70 °C
Mean service life	100000 h
Life L70B10	100000 h
Life L80B10	70000 h
No. switching cycles	>1.000.000
Guarantee	5 years

Specification

Energylabel notice	current label, with EPREL registration
Energy Label A to G	C
Diameter	28.5 mm
Tube diameter	25.4 mm
Length max.	1513 mm
Length	1500 mm
Burning position	any
Mercury content	0.0 mg

Specification

Material	Glass
Shatterproof in accordance with US-food-standard	Yes
Lamp shape	Tube, double-ended
Base	G13
Colour	White

Notes on Operation

Degree of protection (IP)	IP20
Burning position	any
Mode of operation	DC
Range of storage temperature	-20 ... +60°C
Ambient temperatures	-20 ... +50°C
Tc Temperature max.	70 °C

Information especially for EPREL

Energylabel notice	current label, with EPREL registration
Lighting technology	LED
Mains/Non mains connectable	NMLS
Directional or non-directional light	NDLS
Color tunable light source	No
Type of color temperature	SINGLE_VALUE
Color stability MacAdams EPREL	5
EPREL ID number	1083297

Notes

T8 tubular DC LED lamp for external drivers, dimmable with suitable driver, neutral white light, glass bulb, base G13. Exchange for fluorescent lamps.

Please, refer to www.radium.de/recycling for notes on disposal of burned-out lamps as well as lamp breakage.

The "lifespan L70" described for LED lamps indicates the number of hours when the luminous flux has decreased to 70% of its initial value.

The optimal field 'info about service life' contains the frame conditions according to standards based on which the specific service life has been determined. So, for example, "12B50, 50Hz" means that the mean service life (B50) has been determined with a 12h switching cycle at mains (frequency 50Hz), "3B50, HF" is based on a 3h switching cycle at electronic control gear (high frequency).

Base

G13
IEC/EN 60061-1
sheet 7004-51-8

Spectrum

As daylight is a mixture of direct sunlight and light from the sky, the spectral distribution changes all the time due to the time of the day and the weather. The standard illuminant D65 corresponds to daylight with colour temperature of about 6500K.

The colour of coloured LEDs depends on the chemical elements within the light generating chip. The coloured light is generated directly and does not need filtering.

Product data sheet

Gewiss - ELIA PL M2 60x60 840 MICROPR. DALI

Article No.	GWF1611MN840
P	33.0 W
Φ_{Lamp}	-
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	4300 lm
η	-
Luminous efficacy	130.3 lm/W
CCT	4000 K
CRI	80

ELIA is the family of GEWISS products designed for fast and easy installation and with a 5 year guarantee. ELIA PL - Panel LED - is the recessed panel for office and workplace lighting. Luminance and glare control, energy efficiency and comfort are the benefits of this product, for the perfect replacement of traditional lighting installations.

Polar LDC

Glare evaluation according to RUG												
ρ Ceiling	70	70	50	50	30	70	70	50	50	30		
ρ Walls	50	30	50	30	30	50	30	50	30	30		
ρ Floor	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20		
	Viewing direction at right angles to lamp axis					Viewing direction parallel to lamp axis						
Room size X Y												
2H	2H	3H	4H	6H	8H	12H	2H	3H	4H	6H	8H	12H
	15.7	16.9	16.0	17.1	17.4	15.5	16.7	15.8	17.0	17.2		
	16.5	17.6	16.9	17.9	18.2	16.4	17.4	16.7	17.7	18.0		
	17.0	17.9	17.3	18.3	18.6	16.8	17.8	17.2	18.1	18.4		
	17.4	18.3	17.8	18.6	19.0	17.3	18.2	17.6	18.5	18.9		
	17.6	18.5	18.0	18.8	19.2	17.5	18.3	17.8	18.7	19.0		
	17.7	18.6	18.1	18.9	19.3	17.6	18.5	18.0	18.8	19.2		
4H	2H	3H	4H	6H	8H	12H	2H	3H	4H	6H	8H	12H
	16.0	17.0	16.4	17.3	17.7	15.9	16.9	16.3	17.2	17.5		
	17.1	18.0	17.5	18.3	18.7	17.0	17.8	17.4	18.2	18.6		
	17.7	18.5	18.1	18.9	19.3	17.6	18.4	18.0	18.8	19.2		
	18.3	19.0	18.8	19.4	19.9	18.2	18.9	18.7	19.3	19.7		
	18.6	19.2	19.1	19.7	20.1	18.5	19.1	19.0	19.6	20.0		
	18.8	19.4	19.3	19.8	20.3	18.7	19.3	19.2	19.7	20.2		
8H	4H	6H	8H	12H		4H	6H	8H	12H			
	18.0	18.6	18.5	19.1	19.5	17.9	18.6	18.4	19.0	19.4		
	18.9	19.4	19.3	19.8	20.3	18.8	19.3	19.3	19.7	20.2		
	19.2	19.7	19.7	20.2	20.7	19.2	19.6	19.7	20.1	20.6		
	19.6	19.9	20.1	20.4	21.0	19.5	19.9	20.0	20.4	20.9		
12H	4H	6H	8H			4H	6H	8H				
	18.1	18.6	18.5	19.1	19.5	18.0	18.5	18.4	19.0	19.5		
	19.0	19.4	19.5	19.9	20.4	18.9	19.3	19.4	19.8	20.3		
	19.4	19.8	19.9	20.3	20.8	19.3	19.7	19.9	20.2	20.8		
Variation of the observer position for the luminaire distances S												
S = 1.0H	+0.2 / -0.3					+0.2 / -0.3						
S = 1.5H	+0.5 / -0.8					+0.5 / -0.8						
S = 2.0H	+1.1 / -1.0					+1.0 / -1.1						
Standard table	BK05					BK05						
Correction summand	1.7					1.6						
Corrected glare indices referring to 4300lm Total luminous flux												

RUG diagram (SHR: 0.25)

ELIA PL is a LED lowbay for lighting offices, available in square or rectangular versions with a frame in white powder-coated die-cast aluminium and two types of PMMA shield, a high-efficiency micro-prism version with a UGR of less than 19 and an opal version with an UGR of 22. ELIA PL can be flush-mounted in false ceilings with standard panels, or alternatively, can be ceiling or suspension-mounted using the accessories provided separately. The family of products is available with a colour temperature of 3,000K (warm white) or 4,000K (neutral white), a colour rendering index of more than 80 or more than 90 and a separate electronic power supply supplied as part of a kit, in On/Off or DALI versions. ELIA PL is easy to install thanks to the reduced weight of the device and the connector for electrical wiring which enables connection to the remote power supply.

GENERAL INFORMATION

Context	Interior lighting
Luminaire	Modular LED luminaire
Application	Internal
Unique digital code (Datamatrix)	Currently not present
Colour	White
Type of light source	LED
System power	33 W
LED Lifetime	L80B50 (Tq25°) = 50.000h
Weight (kg)	2.4

OPTIC AND ILLUMINATING FEATURES

Optic	Microprismatic
Unified Glare Rating	UGR<19
Lumen output (lm)	4300
Efficacy (lm/W)	130
Colour temperature	4000 K
Colour Rendering Index	CRI 80
Standard Deviation Colour Matching	SDCM = 3
Photobiological Risk Class	RG0
Standard	EN 60598-1; EN 60598-2-2; IEC/TR 62778; EN 62493

Warranty

Warranty	5 years
Stocking temperature	-20° +65°
Operating temperature	-20° +45°

ELETRICAL AND LIGHTING FEATURES

Supply voltage	220-240 V
Rated frequency (Hz)	50 / 60
Driver	External - Included
Driver failure rate	F025 (Tq=25°C) = 50.000 h
Overvoltage protection	DM 1 kV
Control System	DALI

MATERIALS

Body	Aluminium
Shield type	PMMA
Optic	High-efficiency microprism diffuser
Gasket	-
Locking Hook	-

INSTALLATION AND MAINTENANCE

Mounting and installation	Flush (ceiling-mounted and hanging require separately ordered accessories)
Tilt	With suspension adjustment Kit
Wiring	With connection terminal on driver
Fixing	Free-standing or via separately ordered accessories

External screw

External screw	-
Colour	Powder coating

STANDARDS AND APPROVALS

Classification	-
Device with reduced surface temperature	-
DIN 18032-3 certification	Not available
IPEA	-
Insulation class	II
IP degree	IP20 - IP40
Mechanical resistance	IK03
Glow Wire Test	650 °C

Light source replaceability	Non-replaceable
Controlgear replaceability	By professional
Driver Box	-
Maximum surface exposed to the wind	-

DIMENSIONAL

PHOTOMETRIC DISTRIBUTION

TECHNICAL SYMBOLOGY

IP

IP20 - IP40

IK

IK03

GWT

650 °C

Product data sheet

Nexia - OWWL SPOTLIGHT RECESSED 18W / 2000lm / 60° / 4000K

Article No.	26122-XFZ3
P	18.0 W
Φ_{Lamp}	2395 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	2277 lm
η	95.08 %
Luminous efficacy	126.5 lm/W
CCT	3000 K
CRI	90

Polar LDC

Glare evaluation according to RUG												
		70	70	50	50	30	70	70	50	50	30	
p Ceiling		50	30	50	30	30	50	30	50	30	30	
p Walls		20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	
p Floor		20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	
Room size	Viewing direction at right angles to lamp axis	Viewing direction parallel to lamp axis										
X Y												
2H	2H	22.4	23.2	22.7	23.5	23.7	22.4	23.2	22.7	23.5	23.7	
	3H	22.3	23.0	22.6	23.3	23.5	22.3	23.0	22.6	23.3	23.5	
	4H	22.2	22.9	22.5	23.2	23.5	22.2	22.9	22.5	23.2	23.5	
	6H	22.1	22.8	22.5	23.1	23.4	22.1	22.8	22.5	23.1	23.4	
	8H	22.1	22.7	22.4	23.0	23.3	22.1	22.7	22.4	23.0	23.3	
4H	12H	22.0	22.6	22.4	23.0	23.3	22.0	22.6	22.4	23.0	23.3	
	2H	22.2	22.9	22.5	23.2	23.5	22.2	22.9	22.5	23.2	23.5	
	3H	22.1	22.6	22.4	23.0	23.3	22.1	22.6	22.4	23.0	23.3	
	4H	22.0	22.5	22.4	22.9	23.2	22.0	22.5	22.4	22.9	23.2	
	6H	21.9	22.3	22.3	22.7	23.1	21.9	22.3	22.3	22.7	23.1	
8H	8H	21.8	22.3	22.3	22.7	23.1	21.8	22.3	22.3	22.7	23.1	
	12H	21.8	22.2	22.2	22.6	23.0	21.8	22.2	22.2	22.6	23.0	
	4H	21.8	22.3	22.3	22.7	23.1	21.8	22.3	22.3	22.7	23.1	
	6H	21.8	22.1	22.2	22.5	23.0	21.8	22.1	22.2	22.5	23.0	
	8H	21.7	22.0	22.2	22.5	23.0	21.7	22.0	22.2	22.5	23.0	
12H	12H	21.7	21.9	22.2	22.4	22.9	21.7	21.9	22.2	22.4	22.9	
	4H	21.8	22.2	22.2	22.6	23.0	21.8	22.2	22.2	22.6	23.0	
	6H	21.7	22.0	22.2	22.5	23.0	21.7	22.0	22.2	22.5	23.0	
8H	21.7	21.9	22.2	22.4	22.9	21.7	21.9	22.2	22.4	22.9		
Variation of the observer position for the luminaire distances S												
S = 1.0H		+4.2 / -10.6					+4.2 / -10.6					
S = 1.5H		+6.9 / -17.9					+6.9 / -17.9					
S = 2.0H		+8.9 / -26.0					+8.9 / -26.0					
Standard table		BK00					BK00					
Correction summand		3.6					3.6					
Corrected glare indices referring to 2395lm Total luminous flux												

RUG diagram (SHR: 0.25)

OWWL

Technical information / Información técnica:

Index Protection / Índice de protección:	IP20
Driver:	Included / incluido
CRI:	90°
Temperature / Temperatura:	2700K / 3000K / 3500K / 4000K
Lifetime / Tiempo de vida:	65.000h L80B10
Technology / Tecnología:	LED
Guarantee / Garantía:	5 years / años
Class / Clase:	Class II
Voltage / Voltaje:	230V
Flicker:	<5%
Step McAdam:	2-SCDM
Cut-out / Huevo de epotramiento:	Ø100mm

Model:

	Colour	CRI/Temp.	Angle	Led	Dimming
26122-	0 White	H 90/2700K	Z Zoom 20 - 60°	2 1900lm / 12W	- No dimming
	1 Black	E 90/3000K		3 2600lm / 18W	D DALI
		W 90/3500K		4 3600lm / 25W	B Bluetooth
		F 90/4000K		5 4400lm / 33W	

*CRI97 on demand

Owwl Semirecessed
26122-

Owwl Semirecessed
26122-

Quality certificates:

Product data sheet

Not yet a DIALux member - ATLAS-DIR 930 MEDIUM

Article No.	ATLAS-DIR 930 MEDIUM
P	17.5 W
Φ_{Lamp}	1405 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	1321 lm
η	94.03 %
Luminous efficacy	75.5 lm/W
CCT	3000 K
CRI	92

Polar LDC

Cone diagram

Product data sheet

Not yet a DIALux member - ATLAS-IND 930

Article No.	ATLAS-IND 930
P	55.1 W
Φ_{Lamp}	7206 lm
$\Phi_{Luminaire}$	7206 lm
η	100.00 %
Luminous efficacy	130.8 lm/W
CCT	3000 K
CRI	90

Polar LDC

Glare evaluation according to RUG												
	70	70	50	50	30	70	70	50	50	30	30	
ρ Ceiling	50	30	50	30	30	50	30	50	30	30	30	
ρ Walls	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	
ρ Floor												
Room size X Y	Viewing direction at right angles to lamp axis					Viewing direction parallel to lamp axis						
2H	2H	-5.3	-4.8	-4.1	-3.5	-1.7	-5.3	-4.8	-4.1	-3.5	-1.7	
	3H	-3.1	-2.6	-1.8	-1.4	0.5	-3.1	-2.6	-1.8	-1.4	0.5	
	4H	-2.0	-1.5	-0.7	-0.3	1.6	-2.0	-1.5	-0.7	-0.3	1.6	
	6H	-1.0	-0.6	0.3	0.6	2.5	-1.0	-0.6	0.3	0.6	2.5	
	8H	-0.6	-0.2	0.7	1.1	2.9	-0.6	-0.2	0.7	1.1	2.9	
4H	2H	-4.6	-4.2	-3.3	-2.9	-1.1	-4.6	-4.2	-3.3	-2.9	-1.1	
	3H	-2.2	-1.9	-0.9	-0.6	1.3	-2.2	-1.9	-0.9	-0.6	1.3	
	4H	-1.0	-0.7	0.3	0.6	2.4	-1.0	-0.7	0.3	0.6	2.4	
	6H	0.1	0.4	1.4	1.7	3.5	0.1	0.4	1.4	1.7	3.5	
	8H	0.6	0.9	1.9	2.1	4.0	0.6	0.9	1.9	2.1	4.0	
8H	2H	1.7	1.9	3.0	3.2	5.1	1.7	1.9	3.0	3.2	5.1	
	4H	-0.6	-0.4	0.7	0.9	2.8	-0.6	-0.4	0.7	0.9	2.8	
	6H	0.7	0.9	2.0	2.2	4.1	0.7	0.9	2.0	2.2	4.1	
	8H	1.4	1.5	2.7	2.8	4.7	1.4	1.5	2.7	2.8	4.7	
	12H	2.8	2.9	4.1	4.2	6.1	2.8	2.9	4.1	4.2	6.1	
12H	4H	-0.6	-0.4	0.7	0.9	2.8	-0.6	-0.4	0.7	0.9	2.8	
	6H	0.8	1.0	2.1	2.3	4.2	0.8	1.0	2.1	2.3	4.2	
	8H	1.6	1.7	2.9	3.0	4.9	1.6	1.7	2.9	3.0	4.9	
Variation of the observer position for the luminaire distances S												
S = 1.0H	+0.2 / -0.2					+0.2 / -0.2						
S = 1.5H	+0.4 / -0.3					+0.4 / -0.3						
S = 2.0H	+0.5 / -0.5					+0.5 / -0.5						
Standard table	BK10					BK10						
Correction summand	-12.0					-12.0						
Corrected glare indices referring to 7206lm Total luminous flux												

RUG diagram (SHR: 0.25)

ARCHITECTURAL
LIGHTING
DESIGN